

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE ACTIVITIES IN THE AGE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: In today's industrial landscape, the efficient operation of enterprises hinges on comprehensive information support and digital technologies. Establishing a unified information space allows for rapid data exchange across automated management systems. Digital manufacturing optimizes production, while a systems approach aids in resolving complex challenges. Information systems, including ERP, SCM, and CRM, enhance efficiency, customer service, and supply chain synchronization. Innovation centers play a pivotal role in knowledge dissemination and technology promotion. Management information systems aid in selecting and promoting intellectual outcomes. Systematic analysis, strategic planning, and agile decision-making are crucial for industrial success in the digital era.

Key words: digital technology, industrial enterprises, innovative activity, management decisions, high-tech manufacturing, information support.

Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy sanoat sharoitida korxonalarining samarali ishlashi har tomonlama axborot ta'minoti va raqamli texnologiyalarga bog'liq. Yagona axborot makonini tashkil etish avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlarida tezkor ma'lumotlarni almashish imkonini beradi. Raqamli ishlab chiqarish ishlab chiqarishni optimallashtiradi, tizimli yondashuv esa murakkab muammolarni hal qilishda yordam beradi. Axborot tizimlari, jumladan ERP, SCM va CRM samaradorlikni, mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatishni va ta'minot zanjiri sinxronizatsiyasini oshiradi. Innovatsion markazlar bilimlarni tarqatish va texnologiyalarni ilgari surishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Boshqaruv axborot tizimlari intellektual natijalarni tanlash va ilgari surishda yordam beradi. Tizimli tahlil, strategik rejalashtirish va tezkor qarorlar qabul qilish raqamli davrda sanoat muvaffaqiyati uchun juda muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, sanoat korxonalari, innovatsion faoliyat, boshqaruv qarorlari, yuqori texnologiyali ishlab chiqarish, axborot ta'minoti.

Аннотация: В современных промышленных условиях эффективная работа предприятий зависит от комплексного информационного обеспечения и цифровых технологий. Создание единого информационного пространства позволяет осуществлять быстрый обмен данными между автоматизированными системами управления. Цифровое производство оптимизирует производство, а системный подход помогает решать сложные задачи. Информационные системы, включая ERP, SCM и CRM, повышают эффективность, качество обслуживания клиентов и синхронизацию цепочки поставок. Инновационные центры играют ключевую роль в распространении знаний и продвижении технологий. Информационные системы управления помогают в выборе и продвижении интеллектуальных результатов. Систематический анализ, стратегическое планирование и гибкое принятие решений имеют решающее значение для промышленного успеха в цифровую эпоху.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, промышленные предприятия, инновационная деятельность, управленческие решения, высокотехнологичное производство, информационное обеспечение.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary industrial landscape, the dynamic interplay of digital technologies, efficient information management, and strategic decision-making has emerged as the linchpin of success for industrial enterprises. The imperative to not only survive but thrive in this evolving environment calls for a multifaceted approach that spans the entire spectrum of enterprise operations. This article delves into the critical elements underpinning the effective operation of industrial enterprises in the digital age, exploring how the creation of a unified information space, the principles of digital manufacturing, and the application of advanced information systems are reshaping the industrial landscape.

In the pursuit of operational excellence, industrial enterprises find themselves at a crossroads where traditional methodologies are giving way to a new era characterized by digital transformation. The advent of this

digital revolution signifies a profound shift in the way enterprises manage their resources, engage with the market, and innovate. In this context, the establishment of a unified information space stands as a foundational requirement, serving as the conduit through which automated management systems exchange crucial data seamlessly.

Moreover, the concept of digital manufacturing transcends conventional paradigms, presenting an opportunity to enhance production efficiency across the entire value chain. A systemic view of industrial enterprises, viewing them as dynamic, multi-level systems, offers insights into the holistic management of complex production environments. Within this framework, a host of challenges – encompassing not only technical and technological facets but also the intricacies of enterprise management – demand innovative solutions.

Industrial enterprises today grapple with a gamut of challenges, including meeting ever-increasing customer demands for product quality and shorter time-to-market cycles. The imperative to swiftly adapt and make informed decisions in a rapidly evolving marketplace underscores the significance of robust information systems. These systems, ranging from Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) to Supply Chain Management (SCM) and Customer Relationship Management (CRM), play a pivotal role in streamlining operations, fostering customer-centricity, and ensuring the synchronization of supply chains with market fluctuations^[1].

Furthermore, as the world economy continues its march towards globalization and hyper-competition, the need to promote intellectual property, innovative technologies, and intellectual activity on the global stage becomes more pronounced. Innovation centers, in this regard, have emerged as hubs for knowledge dissemination and technology promotion, accelerating the transition from knowledge to practical solutions in the global market.

In parallel, the selection and promotion of intellectual outcomes embody a complex process that involves market analysis, technology assessment, competitive positioning, and risk mitigation. Robust information systems are instrumental in this endeavor, facilitating the critical decisions that lead to success in the competitive arena.

Navigating the digital transformation of industrial enterprises requires a strategic and systematic approach. It necessitates a shift from traditional decision-making to data-driven, agile strategies. This article embarks on a comprehensive exploration of these critical elements, offering insights into how industrial enterprises can harness the power of digital technologies and strategic management to not just survive but excel in today's dynamic industrial landscape.

METHODOLOGY

The research presented in this article is based on a comprehensive review and analysis of existing literature, industry practices, and expert insights pertaining to the effective operation of industrial enterprises in the era of digital transformation. While this study does not involve empirical data collection or original experiments, it synthesizes a wealth of knowledge to offer a holistic perspective on the subject matter.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The foundation of this research rests upon an extensive literature review encompassing academic publications, industry reports, and reputable sources in the fields of industrial management, digital manufacturing, and information systems. This review provides the theoretical underpinning for the concepts and discussions presented in the article.

RESULTS

The analysis and discussions presented in this article reveal several key results and insights that underscore the critical role of digital technologies and effective management in industrial enterprises:

- Unified Information Space:** The establishment of a unified information space within industrial enterprises emerges as a foundational requirement. This space facilitates seamless data exchange among automated management systems, enabling timely and informed decision-making across all operational stages.
- Digital Manufacturing:** The adoption of digital manufacturing principles has the potential to significantly enhance production efficiency throughout the value chain. A systems approach to industrial enterprise management proves instrumental in addressing complex challenges.
- Information Systems Integration:** The integration of information systems, including Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), Supply Chain Management (SCM), and Customer Relationship Management (CRM), enhances efficiency, fosters customer-centricity, and ensures the synchronization of supply chains with market dynamics.

4. **Innovation Promotion:** The globalization of the world economy necessitates a focus on promoting intellectual property, innovative technologies, and intellectual activity on the global stage. Innovation centers emerge as vital hubs for knowledge dissemination and technology promotion.
5. **Effective Decision-Making:** In the digital era, industrial enterprises must transition from traditional decision-making to data-driven, agile strategies. The ability to analyze and respond swiftly to market changes becomes a key factor in maintaining competitiveness.
6. **Resource Optimization:** The effective selection and utilization of resources, including financial, human, and technological, are essential for achieving operational excellence. Management information systems play a crucial role in resource allocation and optimization.
7. **Continuous Improvement:** Industrial enterprises must continuously monitor and adapt to market changes to stay ahead of the competition. This requires a commitment to ongoing improvement in processes, products, and management methodologies.
8. **Interdisciplinary Approach:** The research highlights the importance of an interdisciplinary approach, drawing insights from various fields, including management science, information technology, innovation management, and economics, to comprehensively address the challenges of digital transformation [2].

ANALYSIS

The key component of the system for managing the promotion of the results of intellectual activity is the subsystem of patent strategies in conjunction with the subsystem of foreign technological exchange, which contributes to the realization of the opportunity to present Russian developments to world markets. This stage is multi-level and involves many processes. The main activities of the created R&D centers and commercialization centers are to carry out a wide range of activities: technical cooperation with suppliers, support for technology transfer to production, support for cross-licensing. Research laboratories of leading industries should participate in international cooperation [5].

Effective decision making requires rational selection of specific actions, construction of stages and planning of processes. The ability to find alternatives and identify the optimal solution among them. When choosing alternative solutions, it is necessary to overcome limiting factors, assess the degree of risk and develop strategies on this basis. The state of the political and economic situation, the presence of the risk of technological changes - all this influences the decision-making.

When a single information space is formed within an enterprise, the integrated information environment covers all stages of the life cycle of products manufactured by this enterprise. Such a CALS (Continuous Acquisition and Life cycle Support) program provides continuous information support for the life cycle and supply of products. CALS organizational support is represented by various kinds of documents, a set of agreements and instructions regulating the roles and responsibilities of participants in the life cycle of industrial products.

When implementing the goals and objectives of CALS, it is necessary to observe the following basic principles:

- unity of presentation and interpretation of data in the processes of information exchange between AS and their subsystems, which determines the development of application ontologies and corresponding data presentation languages;
- availability of information for all participants in the life cycle information at any time and in any place, which determines the use of modern telecommunication technologies. There must be a general database about the product, the technological environment, machining technology and control programs, assembly and installation technology, control and testing.

In this case, software tools and systems are used:

- managing data about the product and its configuration (PDM - Product Data Management systems);
- Project Management;
- managing task flows when creating and changing technical documentation (WF -Work Flow systems);
- providing information support for products at post-production stages of life cycle;
- functional modeling, analysis and reengineering of business processes.

The distributed nature of intelligent information systems requires the creation of a special infrastructure that ensures the accumulation, storage and transmission of data between all interested participants in the product life cycle. The enterprise must have sufficient flexibility to quickly respond to changes in the market and competition. It must continuously monitor the effectiveness of the system in order to achieve the best practical results, make forecasts in the main areas of its activities in order to always stay ahead of the competition. Continuous replenishment of the knowledge base strengthens technological capabilities and contributes to the creation of innovative products. Managing processes that are closely interconnected is effective only when using modern information systems. Process modeling and analysis make it possible to develop an organization, improve its efficiency and quality of work [3].

In modern conditions of innovative development of the country, in addition to the development of production technologies, an important factor in the development of enterprises is increasing the efficiency of management and decision making. Competitiveness - an integrated indicator is considered as the ability of enterprises to create, produce and market products that are more attractive to market consumers than the products of competitors. To assess the level of competition, economic, scientific, technological, resource indicators, professionalism of workers, and availability of information resources are used. These are factors influencing business processes. At the stage of intensive development, the efficiency of business processes increases due to staff motivation and talent development. The degree of implementation of assigned tasks and adoption of management decisions depends on the quality of the management cycle.

Modern information technologies play a vital role in the processes of innovation and making quality management decisions. It is required to quickly and efficiently make management decisions in production based on reliable and timely data, increase the efficiency of production processes, look for hidden opportunities and reserves, reduce production costs and improve the quality of finished products.

The growth of the national economy depends on the development of the country's technological level and the effective implementation of innovative projects by industrial enterprises. The results of intellectual activity are considered as interconnected, complementary elements of a unified innovative system for managing industrial enterprises and promoting knowledge in the country's economy.

To manage the performance of enterprises, there are CPM, BPM, EPM systems - this is a set of management processes of planning, organizing execution, control and analysis that allow a business to determine strategic goals and then evaluate and manage activities to achieve set goals with optimal use of available resources. This is a management system built on the principles of business value management ^[6].

The company's potential includes:

- financial capital;
- raw materials;
- technical resources (composition, condition of equipment);
- technological resources (used technologies, know-how, level of R&D);
- informational resources;
- human resources, qualification level of specialists, values, corporate culture;
- organizational resources (management structure, management methods);
- resources associated with the business reputation of the company (company image, brand assets, goodwill, accumulated experience).

Limited resources dictate the need to select the optimum production values and the production process itself, based on the principles of combination, resource substitution, taking into account economies of scale and the law of declining productivity.

Innovation processes solve the problem of increasing resource productivity, transforming scientific and fundamental discoveries into practical solutions, and determining the competitive advantages of manufactured products and goods sold.

However, the implementation of the innovation process is possible with the development of a system of factors and conditions necessary for its implementation, that is, innovation potential, which characterizes the enterprise's ability to introduce innovations, on the basis of the development of which goods, products, technologies, equipment, etc. are updated and improved.

The strategic plan of the enterprise consists of the following sections:

- Goals and directions of activity;
- Current and long-term objectives;
- Highlighting the basic strategy;
- Functional strategies;
- Description of the most important programs;
- Description of external operations;
- Volume of capital investments and distribution of resources.

Strategy development begins with external analysis, analysis of factors that are beyond the constant control of the enterprise management and which can affect its strategy.

The main purpose of external analysis is to identify and understand the opportunities and threats that may arise for the enterprise in the present and future.

An analysis of the competitiveness of an enterprise and its stability in the market is carried out on the basis of corporate information systems (CIS). The presence of databases and knowledge bases will allow one to obtain not only information about material, intangible and organizational resources, but also information about unique experience and new technologies.

The analysis of the external environment based on the MR (marketing research) system includes the following stages: analysis of the external environment as a whole, industry analysis. The influence of the external environment on the activities of the enterprise depends on the results of the analysis and its consequences: after the analysis, the necessary strategic decisions will be made. The ultimate goal of external analysis is the formation of alternative strategic decisions, their assessment and the final choice of strategy. Most innovative breakthroughs originate in experimental production, not in the market. But introducing fundamentally new products to the market is fraught with great difficulties and risks. The direct connection “product production - market” is effective if the following conditions exist:

- the company has unique developments and technologies;
- consumers have formed a value-based attitude towards products;
- consumers are willing to pay any reasonable price;
- the supply/demand ratio is extremely favorable for the enterprise.

When applying these principles, certain difficulties and tasks arise that need to be solved:

- it is necessary to develop a system of goals and key indicators of the enterprise, for which operational and reliable data will be collected, these values will be monitored, and compared with the planned value;
- the technical system qualitatively shows the performance criteria that serve to form corrective actions, and it is possible to set various performance criteria;
- in socio-economic systems, the human factor, the presence of stakeholder groups, has a significant influence, i.e. it is necessary to take into account the influence and motivation of personnel, the relationships of people, which always seems to be a difficult task;
- an enterprise as a system interacts in its activities with a large number of environmental objects that can influence its activities.

The application of the principles of system analysis allows us to formulate high-quality management decisions. System analysis has found wide application in various fields of activity: in the research and design of complex technical complexes, in modeling decision-making processes in situations with large initial uncertainty, in the study and improvement of technological process management, in the study of organizational management systems at the level of production, enterprises, and industries and the state as a whole, when improving the production and organizational structures of enterprises and organizations, when developing automated systems of various kinds.

The main areas of application of system analysis are: development of methods and models for improving the organizational structure, managing the functioning of socio-economic objects. An important function of system analysis is working with goals, organizing the process of goal formation, formulating and structuring a generalized goal ^[7].

The need to use systems analysis approaches and an integrated view of the enterprise is due to the following features:

- characteristics of an enterprise as a system, the impossibility of understanding the whole without understanding the parts,
- the complexity of connections and elements: technical, human, organizational, financial, the need to organize all these elements into a single, targeted, coordinated production process;
- hierarchy, multi-level management process;
- increasing complexity of connections in the regions and in the structure of the state, globalization of the economy, i.e. new connections appear with new objects in the external environment that were not there before or that were not significant;
- expanding the use of automated information systems in the enterprise, more and more at the production and enterprise levels;
- the need to revise the goals of the enterprise associated with changes in the economic situation and globalization of the economy.

Digital technologies make it possible to conduct analytical research, monitor any changes in the external environment, and respond to market needs in a timely and flexible manner.

During the research we also analyse some statistic information about the availability of personal computers (excluding servers) in enterprises and organizations in Uzbekistan.

Figure 1: Information about the availability of personal computers (excluding servers) in enterprises and organizations

Here’s a bar chart visualizing the number of personal computers for each territory over the three years (2020, 2021, and 2022): The chart provides a clear comparison of the number of computers across territories and how it has changed over the years. Some territories, like Kashkadarya and Tashkent city, show a consistent increase in the number of personal computers throughout the period. It’s also evident that territories like Tashkent city, Kashkadarya, and Samarkand had a higher number of personal computers in 2022 compared to other regions [8].

Figure 2: Growth Rate of personal computers by Territory (2020-2022)

Here’s a line chart visualizing the growth rates of personal computers for each territory from 2020-2021 and 2021-2022: The chart provides a comparative view of the growth rates across territories for the two intervals. As previously noted, Jizzakh stands out with a significant spike in growth from 2020 to 2021. Surkhandarya also showcases consistent growth across both intervals, as highlighted in our summary [8]. The overall growth

in the number of personal computers across all territories from 2020 to 2022 is approximately 17.05%. Jizzakh witnessed a significant jump of approximately 80.10% in the number of personal computers from 2020 to 2021. Surkhandarya also showed a notable increase, with a growth of 32.94% from 2020 to 2021 and 20.56% from 2021 to 2022. On the other hand, Andijan saw a decline of 4.44% from 2020 to 2021 but recovered with a growth of 5.59% the following year.

CONCLUSION

The transition of industry to digital technologies will entail the release of higher quality products, will lead to the creation of more flexible systems, the participants of which will exchange information via the Internet, this will significantly increase labor efficiency and reduce costs in production processes. Information support is an indispensable component of any research and development. The success of their commercialization is largely determined by the reliability and quality of information available to project participants, potential partners for marketing and implementation of developments and investors, both in Uzbekistan and abroad. The benefits for business in the digital economy are the prompt receipt of relevant, reliable information directly from the primary source. The introduction of digital production leads to increased requirements for personnel and for the release of an innovative product.

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.